

Insights into the Effects of RbF-PDT on the Absorber Surface of High Efficiency CIGSe Solar Cells and Development of Analytical and Machine Learning Process Monitoring Methodologies Based on Combinatorial Analysis

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Abstract

The latest record efficiencies of the Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGSe) photovoltaic technology have been driven by heavy alkali post-deposition treatments (PDTs). Despite their positive effect, especially in the V_{oc} of the devices, their underlying mechanisms are still under discussion. This work sheds light on this topic by performing a high statistics analysis on 620 high efficiency CIGSe solar cells submitted to four different PDT processes (different RbF source temperature) employing a combinatorial approach based on Raman and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopies. This reveals with statistical confidence subtle differences in the spectroscopic data that relate to the redistribution of defects between the ordered vacancy compound (OVC) and the chalcopyrite phases at the absorber surface. In particular, there is an intertwined decrease of the OVC phase and increase of the so-called “defective chalcopyrite phase”. Additionally, two industry-compatible methodologies for the assessment of the RbF-PDT process and prediction of the V_{oc} of the final devices with a $\pm 2\%$ error and an efficacy of $\sim 95\%$ are developed based on analytical and machine learning approaches. These results show that

the combined Raman and PL spectroscopic techniques represent a powerful tool for the future development of the CIGSe technology at research level and for a more efficient industrial manufacturing.

Keywords: CIGSe solar cells; RbF treatments; combinatorial analysis; machine learning; process monitoring

1. Introduction

Thin film photovoltaic (PV) technologies based on Cu(In,Ga)Se_2 (CIGSe) have reached an advanced degree of maturity with a record energy conversion efficiency at the laboratory scale of 23.35%.^[1] These efficiency values combined with the inherent advantages of thin film PV such as low material usage, fabrication versatility, and their easy integration (e.g. building integrated photovoltaics, wearables, internet of things, etc.) open the way to the democratization and ubiquity of PV through mass production of cheap and efficient solar cell devices. In this regard, CIGSe-based thin film solar cells have been proven viable for large-scale industrial development.^[2]

Recently, efficiency improvements of this type of solar cells have been achieved by applying post-deposition treatments (PDTs) based on heavy alkali elements such as K,^[3–9] Rb,^[5,8,10] and Cs.^[5,8,11] On the one hand, this efficiency improvement is explained by the increase of the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) which has been reported by many authors when applying heavy alkali PDT on a wide range of CIGSe-based absorbers.^[4–10,12,13] On the other hand, the short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) shows different behaviors when heavy alkali PDT is applied.^[3,5,13,14] For instance, the J_{sc} has been shown to depend strongly on the characteristics of the buffer layer deposited after the PDT.^[14] Finally, it has not been possible to clearly determine the impact of the PDT on the fill factor (FF).^[3,5,11,15,16] Thus, the results reported in the literature suggest that the main effect of the heavy alkali PDT is produced on the V_{oc} , while the other optoelectronic parameters can be influenced by several other aspects of the technological processes.

In general, there are no doubts about the benefits of applying heavy alkali PDT on CIGSe-based devices for achieving high efficiencies, but the reasons for the positive impact of this treatment remain under discussion. Previous to the use and study of heavy alkali elements, it was determined that good efficiencies cannot be achieved without the presence of the light alkali Na in the CIGSe absorber.^[17–24] This was attributed to Na-induced higher net doping levels that improve the V_{oc} and the FF .^[19] For light alkali metals such as Na and Li, the diffusion via copper

vacancies (V_{Cu}) and the diffusion via interstitial positions in the lattice have comparable energy barriers, thus it was shown that Na can either replace vacant Cu places or occupy interstices in the crystal lattice of CIGSe.^[25] However, for heavy alkali metals, such as rubidium, the energy barrier is much lower for the diffusion via V_{Cu} than for the diffusion via the interstitial positions.^[25] As a consequence, under Cu-poor conditions, Rb will have a preference to occupy vacant Cu sites, in particular the ones located near the grain boundaries (GBs) or at the surface of the CIGSe absorber, since the large atomic radius of Rb prevents its deeper penetration into the CIGSe grains. In a stoichiometric CIGSe lattice, it is not probable for Rb to replace Cu due to the low availability of vacancies, and it will remain outside the CIGSe grain.^[12,25] Taking this into account, it has been proposed that the positive impact of Rb on the V_{oc} for CIGSe with $[Cu]/([Ga]+[In])$ (CGI) ≥ 0.8 can be attributed to a Rb-Na exchange mechanism in which Rb is accumulated at the GBs and displaces Na towards the interior of the grain, thus leading to improved carrier concentrations.^[26] In addition, the passivation of the GBs by Rb itself would lead to increased carrier lifetimes.^[26] In the case of very Cu-poor CIGSe (CGI < 0.8), Rb could diffuse directly into the V_{Cu} of the Cu-poor material, thus forming the $RbInSe_2$ phase.^[26] Since, in this case, there is no Na-Rb exchange nor GB passivation, the V_{oc} and FF of the devices would be reduced due to the formation of a $RbInSe_2$ layer that would act as a photocurrent barrier.^[12,26] In addition, although the CIGSe surface is modified by RbF-PDT, it has been proposed that such surface modifications do not have an important influence on the performance improvement, but that this improvement is mainly due to a reduction of the amount of tail states, which reduces the non-radiative recombination in the bulk of the absorber.^[12] On the other hand, Refs. [26], [27] and [28] show that the quality modifications of the absorber surface due to PDT strongly depend on the CGI ratio, which implies that they could be either positive or negative depending on the absorber composition.

From all the exposed above, it renders clear that a deeper understanding of the fundamentals behind heavy alkali PDT and its influence on device performance could be of great help for the CIGSe community providing a powerful insight that allows optimizing the fabrication process of high efficiency devices. In this regard, the main aim of the present study is to shed light on the influence of RbF-PDT on the absorber surface in high efficiency CIGSe devices. In order to provide statistically reliable results, a high number of solar cells were fabricated with four different RbF-PDT conditions (620 cells in total: 140 Rb-free cells and 160 Rb-containing for each of the three remaining PDT conditions). A combinatorial analysis was performed in all the cells by means of spectroscopic (Raman and photoluminescence) and optoelectronic characterization. The thorough analysis of the experimental data allows to propose a novel

model for understanding the mechanisms that drive the positive effects of RbF-PDT that is based on the redistribution of structural defects at the absorber surface promoted by the PDT process. This model is further supported by results on charge carrier distribution in the space charge region obtained by capacitance-voltage measurements. Finally, this work also presents the development of process monitoring methodologies compatible with industrial environments that are able to predict the V_{oc} of CIGSe devices exposed to RbF-PDT at the earliest possible stage of the fabrication process. Two methodologies, one based on an analytical approach and another on machine learning algorithms, are proposed using the large set of experimental Raman and photoluminescence (PL) data obtained in this work, showing the high potential of these fast and non-destructive techniques to be used for advanced in-line process monitoring of the CIGSe solar cell production process. These non-destructive methodologies are of great relevance for the CIGSe PV industry since they allow to optimize the manufacturing process in terms of production yield and device efficiency leading to a fabrication process with lower costs and environmental impact.

2. Results and Discussion

The following results and discussions are separated into three subsections. The first subsection shows the results of the evolution of the optoelectronic properties of all the measured solar cells with the RbF source temperature. The second provides the experimental results of the Raman and PL analyses and correlates them with the electrical and optoelectronic properties allowing to propose a model that explains the influence of the RbF-PDT process on the absorber surface. Finally, the third subsection presents a possible application of the obtained results for the prediction of the V_{oc} of the solar cells based on both analytical and machine learning (ML) approaches, revealing the potential of Raman-PL based methodologies for the fine monitoring of the production process of CIGSe-based devices exposed to RbF-PDT.

2.1. Evolution of the Optoelectronic Properties

The evolution of the optoelectronic properties of the 620 analyzed solar cells shows that for low RbF availability (490 °C RbF source temperature), the overall device performance decreases with the PDT falling from an average (maximum) efficiency of around 16.5% (17.9%) for the Rb-free samples to 15.5% (16.9%) for the treated samples (see **Figure 1a** and **Table S1**). As the RbF availability (source temperature) increases, the performance of the samples starts to recover with a 16.3% (17.9%) average (maximum) efficiency for the 520 °C samples, and surpasses the performance of the untreated sample for the 540 °C samples with a 17.1% (18.2%)

efficiency. This evolution seems to be controlled by the FF of the devices that follows an almost exactly similar tendency than the efficiency (Figure 1d). Likewise, the V_{oc} also shows a similar trend with the average (maximum) V_{oc} decreasing from 695 mV (708 mV) in the Rb-free sample to 687 mV (697 mV) in the 490 °C sample and, then, increasing to 697 mV (706 mV) for 520 °C and to 707 mV (721 mV) for 540 °C (Figure 1b). These tendencies are analogous to a previous work by Kodalle et al. carried out in samples fabricated using a similar process but in which the amount of RbF in the samples was controlled by the PDT process duration.^[27] On the other hand, the J_{sc} shows a different trend in both works. While in [27] no significant correlation was found, the present work shows a clearly decrease of J_{sc} with the increasing RbF source temperature (Figure 1c). This incongruence, however, can be explained by the limited number of cells analyzed in [27] (15 cells per PDT condition) that may have prevented to observe a clear trend for such small variations of J_{sc} . In this regard, it is worth noticing the importance of analyzing a large number of samples in this type of studies, in which the variations of the optoelectronic properties of the solar cells are small ($\sim 2.8\%$ for V_{oc} and $\sim 1.2\%$ for J_{sc} in the present work), and where only high statistics enable to unveil trends with statistical confidence.

Figure 1. Evolution of the (a) efficiency, (b) open circuit voltage, (c) short circuit current and (d) fill factor of the 620 solar cells exposed to RbF-PDT with different RbF source temperature. The meaning of each element represented in the box plots is presented in the legend of panel (a). The curves attached to each box plot represent the Gaussian distribution of the displayed data points.

In summary, the optoelectronic results obtained in this work are comparable with the state of the art devices^[29,30] and prove the effectivity of the RbF-PDT that, when performed in optimum conditions, allows to increase the performance of high efficiency CIGSe devices (by more than 3.5% in average, in the present work) thanks, mainly, to an improved V_{oc} and FF .

The complex behavior of the J_{sc} , FF and efficiency that may depend on a wide variety of parameters (e.g. CdS growth, contacts, electric probing...) prevents their use for further correlations of the PDT process with the changes that occur in the CIGSe absorber layer. Thus, the main focus in the further investigations presented below will be put on the correlation of the different physicochemical properties of the CIGSe material with the V_{oc} of the final devices, as this parameter is mainly characterized by the intrinsic changes in the absorber layer and reflects any slight modifications that may occur in it.

2.2. Redistribution of Defects at the Absorber Surface

In order to correlate the optoelectronic properties of the samples with different PDT treatment with their physicochemical properties, all the cells of the different samples were evaluated by Raman spectroscopy using a 638 nm excitation (see *Experimental Details and Methodology* section for further details). Raman spectroscopy already demonstrated its high potential to detect the small structural^[31,32] and compositional^[33–37] modifications in CIGSe compounds which, according to previous investigations of the PDT process, have been identified as critical parameters that might result in the enhancement of the final device performance.^[12]

The high efficiency of the analyzed devices presupposes a good quality of the CIGSe absorber layers in terms of morphology, homogeneity, crystalline quality, and absence of any detrimental secondary phases or strong deviations from the optimal compositions. In this context, no significant changes in the Raman scattering spectra of solar cells exposed to different PDTs were expected. **Figure 2a** shows average normalized (to the intensity of the main peak of CIGSe at 177 cm^{-1}) spectra of samples that underwent PDT treatments with the RbF source at the maximum (540 °C) and minimum (490 °C , note that for 300 °C no PDT process takes place) temperatures. A typical CIGSe compound Raman spectrum is obtained independently of the PDT temperature (e.g., see Refs. [32] and [36–39]) with extremely small deviations between them. However, the high quality of the spectra allows to detect and define through spectra subtraction (blue line in Figure 2a) the main spectral regions where the differences due to the different PDT process appear. These were mainly found in the ranges highlighted in different colors in Figure 2a, specifically in: 1) $150 - 165\text{ cm}^{-1}$; 2) $205 - 233\text{ cm}^{-1}$; and 3) $238 - 260\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is worth noticing, that the first spectral range contains mainly the A_1 symmetry peak of the

OVC phase at $\sim 160 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [40-42] with a slight contribution of a tail of the main A_1 symmetry peak of CIGSe at 177 cm^{-1} . The peaks in the second and third spectral ranges are assigned to E/B-like symmetry modes, that have two mode behavior in the Cu(In,Ga)Se_2 solid solution. [40-43] This implies that the peaks in the $205 - 233 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range are associated with the presence of In cations, while the peaks in the $238 - 260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range relate to the presence of Ga cations. Moreover, in both ranges, the E/B-like symmetry peaks of the OVC phase are overlapped with those of the CIGSe phase, [41] resulting in a complex structure of the Raman spectra in the high wavenumber spectral ranges so the changes observed in these ranges can have different nature. Additionally, for the further upcoming analysis, all the integrated intensities of the defined ranges were normalized to the integrated intensity of the main CIGSe peak calculated in the $165 - 185 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. The general shape of the spectral difference line between the two extreme RbF source temperatures highly resembles that of the OVC CuIn_3Se_5 compound Raman spectrum with a slightly increased intensity of the peaks in the high wavenumber range ($>240 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and shift of the peaks to higher wavenumbers due to the partial substitution of In cations by Ga. [32,40,44] This indicates that the main change occurring at the surface of the absorber due to the different RbF source temperatures is related to the change of the relative amount of the OVC phase ($\text{Cu(In,Ga)}_3\text{Se}_5$), that is usually formed at the CIGSe/CdS interface. [26,32,36,39,45,46] As mentioned above, from the three defined spectral ranges, only the first one ($150 - 165 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is mainly related with the OVC phase without a strong overlap with the Raman peaks of the chalcopyrite CIGSe phase, and with only an insignificant overlapping influence of the tail of the main chalcopyrite Raman peak at 177 cm^{-1} . [32,36-39] Taking this into account, the correlations between the integrated intensity of this OVC-related range and the two other spectral ranges were analyzed in order to study in more detail the variation of the different phases present at the absorber layer. The correlations obtained (see **Figure S1**) show that the variations in the intensity of the peaks in the $205 - 233 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range correlate with the intensity change of the OVC peak, while no correlations were found in the case of the $238 - 260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. This suggests, that the main changes in the $205 - 233 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range are also related to the change of the OVC phase content at the absorber surface, and for the following analyses the sum of the integrated intensities of the $150-165 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $205-233 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral ranges was used as an indicator of the overall change attributed to the variations in the OVC phase content, thus defining $A_{\text{OVC}} = A_{150-165} + A_{205-233}$. On the other hand, the changes in the $238 - 260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range have a more complex nature and are related to small changes in the chalcopyrite phase that will be discussed later on.

Despite the extremely small differences between the Raman spectra of the samples exposed to the different PDTs, the high quality spectra and high statistics of the data allowed to detect clear variations with the RbF source temperature of the relative integrated intensity of the OVC and CIGSe related peaks, i.e. $A_{OVC}/(A_{OVC}+A_{CIGSe})$ (Figure 2b). Moreover, a clear tendency of the V_{oc} value of the solar cells that increases with the decreasing value of A_{OVC} was found (Figure 2c). The linear fitting of these data results in an R^2 value equal to 0.40, which, however, significantly improves (up to 0.63) when only the RbF-treated samples are taken into account (i.e. excluding the Rb-free sample). This suggests a rather abrupt change between samples with and without PDT and a more marked tendency within the RbF-treated samples related to the gradual change of the PDT conditions.

Figure 2. (a) Average Raman scattering spectra of CIGSe-based devices exposed to different RbF-PDTs measured under 638 nm excitation wavelength. The spectrum obtained from subtracting the spectra is also included. The different spectral ranges selected for the analysis are highlighted in colors. (b) Relative integrated intensity of the OVC-related Raman peaks in function of the source temperature of the RbF-PDT. (c) Dependence of V_{oc} of CIGSe solar cells with different RbF-PDT on the relative integrated intensity of the OVC-related Raman peaks.

The influence of the PDT processes on highly defective OVC was previously studied by several groups.^[26,47,48] However, the results are quite contradictory, which is mainly related to the dissents in the question whether this phase is required or not to achieve a positive effect of the PDT. The most systematic study was performed by Kodalle et al.,^[26] where the decrease of the OVC phase is explained by its “partial consume” during the PDT process, that promotes the formation of the RbInSe₂ phase. However, this was clearly observed only in samples with medium or high amount of OVC ($CGI < 0.8$), where the PDT had mainly negative effects on the overall solar cell performance.^[26] On the other hand, for $CGI \geq 0.8$, which is the range typically employed for high efficiency devices, the PDT treatment usually leads to an improvement of device efficiency due to an improvement of the V_{oc} (see the *Introduction* section for further details), which also matches with the decrease of the OVC content, in accordance with the results of this work and Refs. [26] and [47]. All this leads to two unclear points:

- i) It is commonly agreed that the PDT causes Cu-depletion at the absorber surface^[3,27,28,47,49–51] which should therefore increase the OVC phase. However, this effect is not experimentally observed.
- ii) What is the actual mechanism for the decrease of the OVC phase?

According to recent studies, the reduction of the OVC phase is due to the formation of Alkali-In-Se phases at the surface of the absorber (RbInSe₂ in [26] and K-In₂Se₃ in [47]) through the substitution of Cu cations and/or Cu vacancies by alkalis. Some indirect evidences of the formation of this phase have been published recently.^[50,52] However, the discussions about their presence are still open.^[12] Moreover, according to device simulations, the presence of high band gap n-type RbInSe₂ phase at the interface between the absorber and buffer layers should have none or a negative effect on the FF of the CIGSe solar cells without influencing the V_{oc} and J_{sc} .^[26,53] Thus, RbInSe₂, even when formed, is not expected to be the main driving force behind the beneficial influence of RbF-PDT in high efficiency CIGSe-based devices with low amount of OVC.

In order to deepen into the process that leads to the observed decrease of the OVC phase content at the CIGSe absorber surface, the Raman analysis was completed by measurements under a 785 nm excitation wavelength (**Figure 3a**). This excitation wavelength results in pre-resonant conditions for both the chalcopyrite and OVC phases and allows a better detection of the changes in their relative content.^[32,44] Only ten representative cells for each RbF source temperature were analyzed under these conditions (see *Experimental Details and Methodology*). All the spectra were deconvoluted to individual Lorentzian peaks (Figure 3b shows an example

of the standard fitting routine) and their relative integrated intensity was correlated with the V_{oc} of the solar cells. From all the peaks obtained in the deconvolution, only the peaks at 246 and 250 cm^{-1} showed clear correlations with the V_{oc} values of the solar cells. The peak at 246 cm^{-1} shows an inverse correlation in intensity with the increasing V_{oc} (see Figure 3c) similar to that previously found between the V_{oc} and the relative integrated intensity of the OVC peaks (Figure 2c). In typical Ga-free OVC (CuIn_3Se_5) spectra measured under 785 nm excitation reported in the literature, the most intense peak representative of this compound is E/B symmetry peak at 235 cm^{-1} .^[32,44] The peak observed in the present work at 246 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the same E/B-like symmetry peak, but shifted to higher wavenumbers due to the incorporation of Ga atoms in the CuIn_3Se_5 system, that results in the contraction of the interatomic bonds and, as consequence, in the increase of the phonon energy.^[41] As such, it can be directly assumed that the changes in the relative integrated intensity of the peak at 246 cm^{-1} are related to the decrease of the OVC phase discussed above.

Figure 3. (a) Average Raman scattering spectra of CIGSe-based devices exposed to different RbF-PDTs measured under 785 nm excitation wavelength. (b) Example of standard routine for the fitting of Raman scattering spectra measured under 785 nm excitation wavelength. (c-d) Dependence of V_{oc} of CIGSe solar cells exposed to different RbF-PDT on the relative integrated intensity of the peaks at (b) 246 and (c) 250 cm^{-1} .

On the other hand, the peak at 250 cm^{-1} shows a direct correlation in intensity with the increasing V_{oc} (Figure 3d). This peak can be assigned to an E/B symmetry mode of the CIGSe phase and its variations can provide more information about changes in this phase. Here, two effects can be considered. The first one is related to possible increase of the Ga content. This would increase slightly the band gap of the absorber leading to a better coupling with the 785 nm excitation wavelength and, in turn, to a more pronounced pre-resonant effect that results in an increase of the intensity of the LO component of the E symmetry modes. However, this contradicts many authors who claim a small Ga-depletion at the absorber surface after the PDT process,^[27,49,50,54] and, thus, this is not expected to be the case in our samples either. Moreover, comparing the RbF-treated cells with the Rb-free one, it can be clearly observed that the intensity of the peak at 250 cm^{-1} increases without an increase (in case of $520\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) or even a decrease (in case of $490\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) of the V_{oc} , which also indicates that changes in the relative intensity of this peak cannot be directly associated to the Ga depletion at the absorber surface. The second effect that can influence the intensity of the peak at 250 cm^{-1} is related to a change in the chalcopyrite phase due to an increase of point defects. A recent publication reported the analysis of the Raman scattering spectra of the CuInSe_2 and CIGSe compounds under a 785 nm excitation wavelength, and showed an increase of the relative intensity of a peak in the high wavenumber range (indicated as overlapped E/B symmetry peaks of both CIGSe and OVC phases in Figure 3a of the present work).^[44] This was explained by the formation of a so-called “defective chalcopyrite phase” that exists mainly under slightly Cu-poor conditions and differs from the standard stoichiometric chalcopyrite phase with a lower Cu content and higher amount of point defects (V_{Cu} , In_{Cu} and Cu_{In}) in the chalcopyrite structure.^[44] The existence of this phase also matches with recent results from the *first-principle calculation* of the density of state (DOS) of CIGSe absorbers with and without KF-PDT that were correlated with the experimentally derived hard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.^[55] In the case of the PDT-free samples, the authors simply used the combination of DOS from standard stoichiometric CuInSe_2 and of CuIn_5Se_8 phases to fit the experimental results, where the latter represented the OVC at the absorber surface. However, after the KF-PDT, a more complex approach was proposed to better fit the experimental data in which a new “slightly Cu-rich CuIn_3Se_5 ” phase was combined with the KInSe_2 phase. Combining the results from the Raman scattering analysis^[44] and the DOS fitting,^[55] it can be concluded that there exists some distortion in the chalcopyrite phase due to the PDT process. This allows to propose a novel model that explains the positive effect of the RbF-PDT through the redistribution of point defects out of the OVC phase into the defective chalcopyrite phase at the absorber surface. Thus, as the OVC decreases

the defective chalcopyrite phase increases. As such, the increase of the defective chalcopyrite leads to the enhancement of the V_{oc} of the solar cells. The exact mechanism of this beneficial influence is still not clear and requires a separate more detailed study, but it was clearly observed in Ref. [44] and in the present study in devices fabricated following completely different technological routes which may imply that it is a universal feature of the CIGSe material. In summary, the results from the advanced Raman spectroscopy analysis show that the main effect of the RbF-PDT on the CIGSe absorbers is the intertwined decrease of the OVC phase and increase of the defective chalcopyrite phase.

Figure 4. (a) PL spectra of CIGSe-based devices exposed to different RbF-PDT temperature. (b) Relative QY of the PL in function of the RbF-PDT source temperature. (c) V_{oc} in function of the relative QY of the PL band.

The radiative properties of the CIGSe-based solar cells exposed to different PDTs were analyzed by means of photoluminescence spectroscopy. The typical PL spectra of samples exposed to the different PDTs are presented in **Figure 4a** and represent a broad emission band which, in the case of Cu-poor chalcopyrite type compounds, is usually related to the close-to-fundamental radiative recombination edge: free-to-bound (with shallow acceptor level) or

band-to-tail.^[56–59] The increase of the PDT source temperature clearly resulted in an increase of the relative quantum yield (QY) (Figure 4b), as well as in the blue shift of the PL band maximum and in the increase of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) (see **Figure S2**). The QY rise is explained by the increased amount of radiative recombination, which can be related to an increased concentration of beneficial point defects (the defects that contribute in radiative recombination) or to a decrease of the concentration of detrimental point defects (the defects that contribute in non-radiative recombination). Previously, the increase of the relative PL QY due to PDT was associated with the passivation of donor-like defects (V_{Se} and In_{Cu}) that contribute in the appearance of deep donor levels,^[60–62] and correlates with the decrease of the concentration of detrimental defects mentioned above. However, the existence of the deep donor levels does not correlate with the high efficiency of the reference device in this work (close to 18 %) which is higher than those reported in Refs. [60] and [61]. Moreover, in these works the existence of deep donor levels was reflected in the PL spectra by the appearance of a band related to donor-acceptor recombination,^[61] which is not the case in the present study. In this regard, it can be assumed that in the case of high efficiency devices, the PDT has a slightly different effect and that the increase of the QY is rather related to the increase of beneficial defects at the absorber surface. This assumption about surface defects, however, does not contradict the conclusions of Ref. [12] where a PDT-related decrease of the detrimental defects in the bulk of the absorber was proposed based on different experimental and calculation approaches. The above mentioned surface beneficial defects are most probably related to copper vacancies (V_{Cu}) that contribute to radiative recombination and define the p-type conductivity of chalcopyrite-type compounds.^[61] The increase of the beneficial defects also correlates with the aforementioned increase of the FWHM of the PL band after PDT, and is further confirmed by the correlation between the changes in the PL and Raman spectra: an inverse correlation of the relative PL QY is observed with the increasing relative intensity of the OVC Raman peaks (Figure S2c), as well as a direct correlation of the QY with the increasing relative intensity of the defective chalcopyrite phase Raman peak (Figure S2d). It is worth noticing that the observed PL band is related strictly to the emission of the CIGSe phase, while no PL emission of the OVC phase was observed in the analyzed samples which is usually blue-shifted.^[63] Thus, the increase of the relative QY of the PL band with the increase of the temperature of the RbF source, that is explained by the increase of beneficial defects, is strongly connected to the changes occurring in the chalcopyrite phase, while changes in the OVC phase is a secondary associated effect. Finally, a clear direct correlation of the relative QY and the V_{oc} of the solar cells (Figure 4c) is also in accordance with such a model that explains the effect of PDT on the

absorber surface. Similarly to the analysis performed above of the dependence of the V_{oc} on the OVC content, the linear fitting of the data in Figure 4c results in a higher R^2 value when the Rb-free cells are not taken into account (0.63 versus 0.47, when all points are included in the fitting).

Figure 5. Variation of the apparent hole concentrations in cells exposed to different PDT measured by C - V (a) without and (b) with applied bias voltage.

The variation in defect concentration was further investigated by studying the capacitance properties of representative solar cells from the different sets of samples exposed to different PDTs. Extracted from the capacitance-voltage (C - V) measurements, the values of the apparent hole concentration (see calculation details in the *Supporting Information*) showed a clear decrease with the increasing PDT source temperature (**Figure 5a**). These results, even if in accordance with several previously published results^[19,64] and able to contribute to the observed decrease of the J_{sc} in the solar cells exposed to the PDT (Figure 1c), do not strictly support the previous conclusions regarding the increase of the beneficial defects (associated to an increase of V_{Cu}) since this would be expected to also increase the hole concentration. In order to define the origin of such inconsistency, the C - V measurements were performed by applying different bias voltages. The positive value of the bias voltage, which results in a decrease of the effective depletion width thus allowing to collect information closer to the absorber-buffer interface, shows an opposite dependence of the apparent hole concentration with the PDT source temperature (Figure 5b) compared to the non-bias voltage case (Figure 5a). This denotes that the effect of RbF-PDT in the hole concentration is different in the absorber bulk and at the surface. Further fine correlations of the apparent hole concentration at the absorber surface with the relative QY of the PL emission and with the amount of defective chalcopyrite phase found from Raman scattering analysis (Figure S3) support the model proposed above based on the increase of defect concentration with the PDT that is originated by the redistribution of defects

out of the OVC phase and, probably, also out from the absorber bulk to the chalcopyrite phase at the absorber surface.

The results and discussions presented here, that show the relatively high importance of surface modifications in the absorber layer due to PDT (mainly the absorber surface and close to surface layers are analyzed by the Raman and PL measurement conditions used, see *Experimental Details and Methodology* section), add new findings to the conclusions previously published in a review article co-authored by researchers from several groups.^[12] In this review article the authors could not define any clear correlations between the absorber surface modifications and the beneficial effect of the alkali PDT, which has been overcome in the present work mainly thanks to the high statistics employed. Some publications by Kaufmann et al.^[27,28] also show the importance of the absorber surface modifications, which, however, can have either a positive or negative effect on device performance, mainly depending on the CGI ratio. The analysis presented in this work does not exclude any beneficial effects of the alkali PDT on the CIGSe bulk, but allows to conclude that the surface modifications, even if of high importance, are quite small when dealing with high efficiency devices, and their detection requires high statistics and complex data analysis. These are omitted by some of the researchers or are impossible to be implemented due to the complexity and time consuming nature of the applied characterization techniques. In this case, the spectroscopic approach proposed here, based on combined Raman and PL analysis, can be a key for the further development of research on complex semiconductor materials based on high statistics of experimental data.

2.3. Development of Process Monitoring Methodologies

From the analytical analysis of the data presented in the previous section, it is possible to propose a fast and non-destructive methodology for the monitoring of the RbF-PDT process and the prediction of the solar cell performance, specifically of the V_{oc} , at early stages of device manufacturing. In the following, the optimum V_{oc} is defined to be 705 mV and the objective of the process monitoring methodology is to be able to detect deviations of about $\pm 2\%$ from that value, with that V_{oc} range selected as the criterion for “high V_{oc} ”.

Regarding the analytical process monitoring methodology for V_{oc} prediction, it is proposed to use the high statistical analyses performed in this work with Raman and PL spectroscopies since they show a clear dependence of the V_{oc} with the analyzed parameters: relative amount of OVC phase (Raman) and relative QY (PL) (see Figures 2c and 4c). However, both dependences present a relatively high dispersion that limits their independent use for the fine prediction of the V_{oc} (the R^2 value for the linear fitting of the results in both cases did not exceed 0.63). In

order to overcome this limitation, the proposed process monitoring analytical methodology for predicting the solar cell V_{oc} is based on a more advanced correlation using the combination of both parameters, the OVC content and the relative QY of the PL, in a 3D correlation graph (see **Figure 6**, third dimension for the V_{oc} represented by color). From the 3D correlation graph, two specific regions can be defined (green and orange dashed rectangles in Figure 6). The green rectangle contains mainly points associated to cells with $V_{oc} \geq 705$ mV while the orange rectangle contains cells with $V_{oc} = 705 \pm 15$ mV (i.e. inside the aforementioned $\pm 2\%$ limit of V_{oc}). For the orange rectangle, the statistical analysis yields a predictive power of the proposed combined methodology (when both Raman and PL data are taking into account) close to 89%, calculated as the percentage of the cells with targeted V_{oc} (705 ± 15 mV) that are inside the rectangle. In addition to this, the predictive power when using only Raman or PL data was also calculated and the obtained percentages are presented in the right panel of Figure 6. Here, it is seen that for the $\pm 2\%$ limit of V_{oc} (705 ± 15 mV), the use of only PL data provides a similar predictive power to the combined Raman and PL approach. However, for the stricter case of predicting cells with $V_{oc} \geq 705$ mV, the predictive power of employing the combined Raman and PL data is 10% (absolute) higher than when information of the separated spectroscopies is used. This may be due to the slightly different sensitivity of Raman and PL spectroscopies to changes at the absorber surface due to the PDT. Be as it may, the analysis presented here clearly demonstrates the potential of the combined Raman and PL approach for the fine prediction of the V_{oc} of the PV devices based solely on spectroscopic data.

Figure 6. Left – 3D plot for the fine monitoring and prediction of V_{oc} value based on Raman and PL data. Right – comparison of the predictive power for two different criteria using separated Raman or PL data or a combination of both. See the main text for more detailed explanation.

Even though most of the evaluation steps of the analytical approach were performed in an automatic way (using the “spectrapepper” library)^[65], some of them still require the implication of highly qualified trained specialists which imposes several limitations for applying this methodology for real in-line or on-line monitoring of a production process. To move further

and to propose a more robust process monitoring methodology, the spectroscopic data obtained in the present study were used for the training and testing of a Machine Learning algorithm. As mentioned in *Experimental Details and Methodology* section, a principal component and linear discriminant analysis (PCLDA) algorithm was used as the most appropriate one for the defined task. The raw Raman and PL spectra were used as features for the algorithm, and two training instances were performed for two different target variables: i) PDT source temperature, and ii) V_{oc} of the final device.

The first selected target variable allows to establish a methodology to monitor the possible deviations of the process from the standard one. For this case, four classification groups were considered in accordance with the four RbF source temperatures used in manufacturing process of the samples employed in this work: 1) 300 °C (Rb-free); 2) 490 °C; 3) 520 °C; and 4) 540 °C. The application of the PCLDA algorithm allowed to obtain good testing scores for each group (**Figure 7**), showing their fine classification, and the possibility to use spectroscopic data for the monitoring of possible deviations in the PDT process.

Figure 7. Results of the PCLDA algorithm using the PDT source temperature as target: (left) decision map and (right) confusion matrix for process prediction.

For the second selected target variable, three main categories were defined for the analysis: 1) $V_{oc} \geq 705$ mV; 2) $705 > V_{oc} \geq 690$ mV; and 3) $V_{oc} < 690$ mV. These three categories correspond to the above defined limit of $\pm 2\%$ deviation from the optimal 705 mV (category 2 and 3) and deviations higher than 2% (category 1). The defined decision criteria (left panel in the **Figure 8**) allowed to classify with relatively high accuracy the test cells based only on their spectroscopic response; $\sim 95\%$ of correct predictions for categories 2 and 3 (see right panel in Figure 8), that provides about $\pm 2\%$ maximum deviation from 705 mV. These results prove the possibility to combine spectroscopic techniques with ML algorithms for establishing a process monitoring methodology for a fine prediction of the V_{oc} value within a 2% error. However, the performance of the ML algorithm could be further improved employing a higher number of training data which would decrease the overfitting of the classified data and improve the test

scores. Additionally, increasing the amount of applied characterization techniques would allow to add additional inputs for the ML algorithms (information about chemical composition, structural properties, etc.) which would certainly lead to the improvement of the predictive power of the methodology. Under these conditions, the main limitation for including further techniques in the ML algorithms in a certain application will be defined by its compatibility with process monitoring (high measurement speed, non-destructiveness, easy integration in industrial lines, etc.).

Figure 8. Results of the PCLDA algorithm using the V_{oc} as target: (left) decision map and (right) confusion matrix for V_{oc} prediction.

The applied PCLDA algorithm reduces the n -dimensional experimental spectroscopic data ($n > 1,500$ for each cell, taking into account the information for each CCD pixel of the measured Raman and PL spectra) to a simpler 2-dimensional representation as shown in Figures 7 and 8. In most cases, this reduction of the dimensions leads to the loss of physical meaning of the discriminants calculated by the ML algorithm. However, the search of a possible physical meaning remains one of the key points in the application of self-learning ML algorithms for the development of materials science. From the two target variables used in the present study, the main interest lies at the discriminants that were obtained by the PCLDA algorithm from the classification of the V_{oc} (Figure 8). Correlating these two discriminants with different physical parameters discussed above it was found that the discriminant $D1b$ correlates with both the relative OVC content and relative QY of the PL band (Figure 9a and b). This suggests that namely these two physical parameters extracted from the input data had a decisive effect on the ML results, and supports the monitoring methodology based on the analytical approach presented above (see Figure 6). The correlation of both parameters with the same $D1b$ discriminant suggests that the variation of a similar property of the CIGSe-based solar cell lies behind the variations of these two parameters, in accordance with the conclusions made above in Section 2.2, and that is related to the formation of a defective chalcopyrite phase. Moreover, the continuous correlation of the V_{oc} and $D1b$ was also established (Figure 9c), which allows

not only to specify the classification group but to directly predict the numerical value of the V_{oc} for a solar cell. In comparison with directly employing the ML V_{oc} discretized group classification shown in Figure 8, this approach allows to predict the numerical value of the V_{oc} in a continuous range. However, it presents an overall lower predictive power (the R^2 value for the polynomial fitting in Figure 9c is equal to 0.68). Such a correlation with the $D1b$ discriminant that is also assigned to the relative content of the defective chalcopyrite phase denotes the critical importance of changes in this phase at the absorber surface during the PDT process. However, it is worth noticing that for low V_{oc} values (< 700 mV) there is a slightly higher deviation of the points from the proposed trend lines in Figure 9 (yellow dotted lines and solid black fitting line). The same feature can also be observed in the analytical analysis of some of the data (i.e. higher scattering of the points in Figure 4c and 6 for $V_{oc} < 700$ mV values). This may suggest that there exist different mechanisms that lead to the improvement of the V_{oc} due to PDT for the very high and medium or low values of this parameter. As already mentioned above, the passivation effect of RbF-PDT of detrimental point defects was already established in the case of relatively low efficiency solar cells,^[60,61] while an additional increase of the beneficial point defects is proposed in the present study. The combination of both mechanisms due to the RbF-PDT can occur in the cells with low or medium V_{oc} . Nevertheless, this hypothesis needs to be further evaluated to define a full picture of the effect of heavy alkalis on the surface and bulk of the chalcopyrite absorbers.

Figure 9. Correlation of the calculated $D1b$ PCLDA discriminant with (a) relative OVC content calculated from the Raman scattering analysis and with (b) relative QY of the PL band. (c) Continuous correlation of the V_{oc} with the $D1b$ discriminant. The dotted yellow lines are only intended as a visual guide for the reader.

3. Conclusions

This work has presented the high potential of combining Raman and PL spectroscopies for the analysis of the effect of RbF-PDT on a high amount of high efficiency CIGSe solar cells which has allowed to reach to two important results. Firstly, that the surface modifications that occur in the CIGSe absorber layer of the high efficiency devices are of great relevance. This conclusion was made based on the advanced analysis of the spectroscopic data obtained under different measurement conditions combined with the electronic and optoelectronic information of the solar cells. As a result, an innovative model has been proposed in which the main driving force behind the improvement of the device performance due to RbF-PDT is related to the redistribution of defects between the OVC and chalcopyrite phases that leads to the formation of the so-called “defective chalcopyrite phase”. All the applied techniques (Raman, PL, *C-V*) support the observed effect of the defect redistribution at the absorber surface as result of PDT process, showing the importance of the formation of the defective chalcopyrite phase. However, the exact mechanism of its influence on the optoelectronic properties, mainly on the V_{oc} , of the solar cells still has to be defined and remains as a challenging tasks for the future studies of CIGSe-based devices. The second result of the performed study is related to the development of industry-compatible process monitoring methodologies for the assessment of the RbF-PDT process and prediction of the V_{oc} of the final devices. Both analytical and ML approaches were established for this task, resulting in process monitoring methodologies that allow to predict the V_{oc} with an error as small as $\pm 2\%$ and an efficacy $\sim 95\%$, and to have a precise control (with the test score $\geq 92\%$) of the PDT temperature. These results show the high potential of the combined Raman and PL spectroscopic techniques and advanced analysis to be used both for fundamental research and for the fast, non-destructive and in-situ monitoring of the CIGSe-based thin film solar cells production process. This represents a very powerful tool for the future development of this promising and environmentally-sustainable PV technology and for a more efficient and precise industrial manufacturing.

4. Experimental Details and Methodology

Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ absorbers were deposited on Mo-coated soda-lime glass (SLG) in a production-like in-line co-evaporation system for substrate sizes up to 30×30 cm² using a multi-stage process. Details of the process can be found in [29]. All the samples were prepared in the same deposition process with different conditions only for the in-situ alkali post-deposition treatment (PDT) realized by varying the RbF evaporation source temperature for different carriers in the

continuous substrate flow of the inline-system with steps at 300 °C (relating to no RbF-PDT), 490 °C, 520 °C, and 540 °C.^[66] As a very rough rule of thumb, it can be estimated that the difference in vapor pressure due to the different RbF source temperatures results in a twice thicker RbF layer for each temperature step (i.e. from 490 to 520 °C and from 520 to 540 °C).

The solar cells were finalized by a 50 nm thick chemical bath deposited CdS buffer layer, 35 nm thick i-ZnO as high resistive layer, 200 nm thick ZnO:Al as transparent front contact, and Ni/Al/Ni grids with ~ 2.5 μm thickness. X-ray fluorescence measurements determined the chemical composition of the absorber with a $[\text{Ga}]/([\text{Ga}]+[\text{In}])$ ratio of about 0.30, a $[\text{Cu}]/([\text{Ga}]+[\text{In}])$ ratio of ~ 0.80 (both with ~ 0.01 error related to the uncertainty of the measurement system) and a thickness of ~ 2.3 μm for all samples.

Each substrate was mechanically scribed into 1.0×0.5 cm^2 individual solar cells and no specific selection of the cells was performed for their analysis (i.e. all the different individual cells were employed for this study). Current–Voltage (I – V) curves of the individual cells were measured with a WACOM AM1.5G solar simulator in four-point geometry at standard testing conditions and a silicon reference cell for calibration.

Raman spectroscopy and photoluminescence (PL) were employed to analyze the structural, compositional and radiative properties of the CIGSe absorber. A special optical probe was developed at IREC to measure the Raman scattering and the PL spectra at the same point quasi-simultaneously using a large area spot (~ 70 μm^2) in order to characterize a representative region of the CIGSe layer. The probe was coupled to high resolution FHR640 Horiba Jobin Yvon spectrometer and a CCD detector cooled to -130 °C for Raman spectra acquisition in back scattering configuration, and to a Sol 1.7 spectrometer from B&W Tek with an InGaAs detector for acquiring the PL data in near-backscattering configuration. The simultaneous Raman and PL characterization was carried out under a 638 nm (solid state laser) excitation wavelength. Additionally, a solid state laser of 785 nm excitation wavelength (leading to quasi-resonant conditions with CIGSe) was used in order to complete the Raman characterization of the absorber layer. It is important to note that the strong PL signal arising from the samples under 785 nm excitation wavelength required special conditions and high acquisition times to obtain high quality Raman spectra preventing to measure the spectra of all the cells studied in this work in a reasonable time. Under this limitation, only ten representative cells for each RbF source temperature were analyzed with these excitation conditions. Laser power densities lower than 150 W/cm^2 were selected for both excitation wavelengths to prevent any thermal effect on the samples. The Raman shift was calibrated using a monocrystalline Si reference by imposing

the position of its main peak to 520 cm^{-1} , and the baseline was subtracted in the spectra prior to the analytical analysis using the ‘bspbaseline’ function from the spectrapepper library.^[65] It should be noted that for both 638 and 785 nm excitation wavelengths, the photon energies are higher than the band gap of the CIGSe absorber ($\sim 1.2\text{ eV}$, taking into account the measured amount of Ga)^[67] leading to a high absorption coefficient and a low penetration depth providing information of mainly the surface ($\sim 50\text{ nm}$ – expected penetration depth of 638 nm laser, taking into account the absorption coefficient of CIGSe)^[68] and the subsurface ($\sim 100\text{ nm}$ – expected penetration depth of 785 nm laser, taking into account the absorption coefficient of CIGSe)^[68] region of the absorber. Thus, the Raman results presented in this work show mainly the influence of RbF-PDT on the CIGSe absorber surface. Regarding PL, it is worth noticing that the specific conditions of the measurements and the applied system do not allow to directly measure the absolute quantum yield (QY) of the emission band, but they allow to define the relative QY, which shows the relative change from one measured point/sample to another. All the spectroscopic measurements were performed in four points for each cell, and the resulting spectra were averaged in one Raman and one PL spectrum per cell. These averaged spectra were used for the analytical analysis approach.

Capacitance-voltage (*C-V*) profiling was performed with a Keysight E4990A Impedance Analyzer in the dark at room temperature. A 50 mV and 345 kHz AC signal was employed in accordance with previously reported *C-V* studies of CIGSe-based solar cells treated with heavy alkali PDT.^[19,64]

A machine learning (ML) driven methodology, based on cascaded principal component and linear discriminant analysis algorithms (PCLDA), was employed to define a robust and easy-to-implement methodology for the monitoring of the PDT process and the prediction of solar cell performance. Both algorithms perform dimension reductions capable of translating high-dimensionality problems into a bi-dimensional one. Their combination provides several benefits, namely the detection of the most important dimensions for the data as a whole and then for each classification group, which provides improved classification results. More in detail, the PCLDA algorithm was selected since it allows to reduce dimensionality not by deleting features but rather by performing linear combinations. In other words, this technique does not perform feature selection and preserves more of the information when the dimensionality is reduced, focusing more on feature extraction. It is worth to mention that other dimension reduction algorithms can be also applied for the analysis performed in this work, and this can be a matter of future considerable investigations. In order to test and implement the ML-based PCLDA algorithms, the Python programming environment with the Scikit-Learn^[69]

and spectrapepper^[65] (developed by IREC for spectral data conditioning and ML support) libraries were employed. As specified above, for each cell Raman and PL spectra were measured simultaneously under the 638 nm excitation conditions in four different points. All these individual spectra (4960 Raman and PL spectra in total) were used as input features, and they were randomly divided in 70% for training and 30% for testing. The PCLDA interface is done by, first, training PCA to reduce dimensionality to 400 and then LDA to translate these 400 dimensions into a 2D space. The test scores were calculated for each category separately by calculating the amount of correct predictions inside each category. This allowed to better understand the possible dependence of the predictive power of the PCLDA algorithm on the value of the V_{oc} and to estimate a possible methodology saturation. The fact that four points per cell were measured allowed to increase the amount of input data (in this case, no cell averaging was made) allowing to minimize the overfitting effect. Moreover, the fact of using raw Raman and PL spectra as input data allows to consider that each pixel of the two detectors (1024 pixel in Raman CCD and 512 pixels in PL InGaAs detector) is a separate dimension, resulting in 1536-dimension data that are reduced to 2-dimensions by the PCLDA algorithm.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the authors.

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